

FORMATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS IN THE TRAINING SYSTEM

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Abstract. *In today's innovative environment, there is a great need for pedagogical personnel with technological competence in the educational system. Taking this into account, this article focuses on the issue of the formation of technological competence of pedagogues in the system of professional development and provides an opinion on the work that should be done for this.*

Keywords: *teacher, training system, technological competence, professional competence, educational efficiency.*

Based on the rich intellectual heritage and universal values of our people, modern culture, economy, science, techniques and technologies, a system of training of mature specialists has been developed and is being rapidly implemented.

The development of our republic and the formation of a socio-economic policy in line with the market economy require the improvement of the content of professional education that meets the requirements of the times and ensures the effectiveness of the processes of training highly qualified pedagogues. This, in turn, creates the need to update the content of continuous education that serves to form the technological professional competence of specialists, to introduce innovative forms and methods of teaching, modern information and communication technologies into practice. On this basis, a number of measures are being implemented in higher education institutions today to improve the quality of education, to ensure the coherence and continuity of educational stages. Including, it can be seen that such work is being carried out on a large scale in educational training centers. Today, humanity is experiencing a series of profound changes. Transformations concern the whole civilization, because they are associated with the dynamic transition from industrial society to post-industrial and information society, in which the processes of creation and dissemination of knowledge are important. These processes are mainly based on the development of potential opportunities of the educational system and their use. The role of the teacher in society is considered in connection with his activities in the system of social relations, their formation and development. The teacher contributes to meeting the needs of society, takes an active part in the creation and understanding of social relations, and thus has a significant impact on the trend of their development. For this reason, today, he is required to flexibly adapt to changing socio-economic conditions, independence, critical thinking, working with growing scientific information, designing a pedagogical process on a diagnostic basis and its effective implementation.

At the same time, the development of the educational system of Uzbekistan is closely related to the theoretical development and practical solution of the problem of developing the professional competence of the teacher. With the radical change of the existing teacher training system, it will be necessary to encourage the pursuit of innovative pedagogical activity and create conditions for independent improvement of professional competence. An individual, innovative and reflexive profession that directs teachers to study and revise their pedagogical experience, to

create and develop a unique pedagogical system, an individual learning style and their professional self. It is necessary to develop forms of development. Development of the basis of the holistic concept of "professional competence" of teachers means determining the level of formation of technological competence as a component of it. In general, increasing professional competence means overcoming one's professional obstacles and difficulties, abandoning established stereotypes of pedagogical activity, and mastering methods of professional self-awareness. As for technological competence, it is a set of skills starting with the design of the pedagogical process, setting the goal, choosing the acceptable and adequate content and methods of the implementation of educational activities, as well as analyzing and considering the compliance with the basic rules of the implementation of the educational process is to master the plan. These include the results obtained with the planned results.

The traditional system of professional development, which is primarily focused on the reproductive methods of acquiring knowledge and improving professional skills, turns out to be ineffective in the conditions of individual components in the structure and does not ensure the real development or formation of the professional competence of teachers as a holistic education.

The analysis of the literature and scientific research on the issue shows that there are a number of contradictions between the pedagogical understanding of the problems of the training system and the modernization of its activities, as well as the real practice data. The need for and lack of continuous nature of education; formation of appropriate relations between specialists in various fields of activity; the need to qualitatively change the theory and practice of the training system aimed at the implementation of the idea of developing specialist training and the priority reproductive level of education in this system; the urgency of forming the teacher's technological competence and the fact that a theoretical model of the organization of the relevant process in the training system has not been developed; The modern pedagogical requirements for the teacher's technological skills to be a subject of pedagogical activity, the lack of development of ways and means of the holistic personal-activity process of developing the teacher's technological competence in the professional development system are clear evidence of this takes. Solving the listed contradictions determined the selection of the central problem, as well as what should be the conditions of the educational process in the training system that helps to effectively form the technological competence of the teacher? drew our attention. Taking into account the urgency of the problem and its insufficient development, the main content of the article was defined as "Formation of technological competence of teachers in the system of professional development of teachers." It was predicted that the results could be achieved by focusing on the identification, development, research and testing of the foundations. It should be noted that the theoretical importance of the turban problem in the center is as follows: the content of the definition of "Teacher's technological competence" is clarified and expanded; the formation of the teacher's technological competence in the structure is based on the general concept of "professional competence"; "the relation of the concepts of "professional competence", "technological competence", "technological competence of a particular teacher" as universal, special and individual is defined; signs of the teacher's technological competence are shown; the principles of forming the teacher's technological competence are formed in the professional development system; the criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of the organizational, pedagogical, didactic and methodological conditions for the formation of the teacher's technological competence are taken into the center of attention.

An important condition for the development of our country is the implementation of an improved system of personnel training based on the development of modern economy, science, culture, technology, and technology. Today's task of education is to teach teachers to be able to work independently in the conditions of the information-educational environment that is growing day by day, to use the flow of information wisely. For this, it is necessary to provide them with the opportunity and conditions for continuous independent research.

In order to increase the effectiveness of the education of the young generation and achieve full acquisition of knowledge, to ensure that the individual is the focus of education and independent learning of future pedagogues, he is well prepared for educational institutions and in his field in addition to solid acquisition of knowledge, we need teachers who know modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods and can use them in organizing educational and educational activities. For this purpose, it is necessary to arm all science teachers with innovative pedagogical technologies and interactive methods, and to improve their skills in applying the knowledge they have acquired in educational activities. At the same time, Future pedagogues should acquire pedagogical knowledge and teaching methods based on the technological approach in addition to the knowledge acquired in their specialties.

Thus, in a short period of time, the delivery of certain theoretical knowledge to students, the formation of skills and competencies in certain activities, as well as monitoring the activities of learners, assessing the level of knowledge, skills and competencies acquired by them requires the teacher to have technological competence and a new approach to the educational process. Taking this into account, it is important not to forget that it is a very important issue to improve pedagogues' aptitude for technological competence in the professional development system, and to implement practical work accordingly.

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